

KOSHI-RIMAN SHARTI VA UNING NATIJALARI.

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ABSTRACT

Biz bu maqolada Koshi Riman shartlari va golomorf funksiyalar haqida to'xtalib o'tamiz va Koshi Riman shartining isboti bilan ko'ramiz va funksiyaning analitik yoki difrensiyalanuvchanlikga tekshirib va uni golomorflikga tekshiramiz.

1-teorema. $f(z)$ funksiyaning z_0 nuqtada $f'(z_0)$ hosilasiga ega bo'lish uchun bo'lishi va tengsizliklarning bajarilishi zarur va yetarli.

Isbot. Zarurligi $f(z)$ funksiya z_0 nuqtada ($z_0 \in D$) $f'(z_0)$ hosilaga ega bo'lsin. Hosila ta'rifiga ko'ra $\lim_{\Delta z \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta f(z_0)}{\Delta z} = f'(z_0)$,
ya'ni

$$\Delta f(z_0) = f'(z_0)\Delta z + \alpha \cdot \Delta z \quad (4)$$

bo'ladi bu yerda

$$\Delta z = z - z_0 = (x + iy) - (x_0 + iy_0) = (x - x_0) + i(y - y_0) = \Delta x + i\Delta y,$$

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta f(z_0) &= f(z) - f(z_0) = [u(x, y) + iv(x, y)] - \\ &- [u(x_0, y_0) + iv(x_0, y_0)] = [u(x, y) - u(x_0, y_0)] + \\ &+ i[v(x, y) - v(x_0, y_0)] = \Delta u + i\Delta v \end{aligned}$$

bo'lib, α esa Δx va Δy larga bog'liq va ular nolga intilganda nolga intiladi:

$$\lim_{\Delta x \rightarrow 0, \Delta y \rightarrow 0} \alpha = 0$$

Endi $f'(z_0)$ hamda α larni

$$f'(z_0) = a + ib, \quad \alpha = \alpha_1 + i\alpha_2 \quad \left(\lim_{\substack{\Delta x \rightarrow 0 \\ \Delta y \rightarrow 0}} \alpha_1 = \lim_{\substack{\Delta x \rightarrow 0 \\ \Delta y \rightarrow 0}} \alpha_2 = 0 \right)$$

deb, (4) tenglikni quyidagicha yozamiz:

$$\Delta u + i\Delta v = (a + ib)(\Delta x + i\Delta y) + (\alpha_1 + i\alpha_2)(\Delta x + i\Delta y)$$

Bu tenglikdan, haqiqiy xamda mavhum qismlarini tenglab topamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta u &= a\Delta x - b\Delta y + \alpha_1\Delta x - \alpha_2\Delta y \\ \Delta v &= b\Delta x + a\Delta y + \alpha_2\Delta x + \alpha_1\Delta y \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Demak, $u(x, y)$ va $v(x, y)$ funksiyalar (x_0, y_0) nuqtada differensiallanuvchi

Ayni paytda $f(z)$ funksiya z_0 nuqtada R^2 ma'noda differensiallanuvchi bo'ladi.

Madomiki, $f(z)$ funksiya z_0 nuqtada, $f'(z_0)$ hosilaga ega ekan,

unda $\Delta z \rightarrow 0$, jumladan $\Delta z = \Delta x \rightarrow 0$ ($\Delta y = 0$), $\Delta z = \Delta y \rightarrow 0$ ($\Delta x = 0$)

bo'lganda ham

$$\frac{\Delta f(z_0)}{\Delta z}$$

nisbatining limiti har doim $f'(z_0)$ ga teng bo'laveradi, (5) tengliklar

$\Delta z = \Delta x$ ($\Delta y = 0$) bo'lganda

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta u &= a\Delta x + \alpha_1\Delta x \\ \Delta v &= b\Delta x + \alpha_2\Delta x \end{aligned} \quad (6)$$

$\Delta z = \Delta y$ ($\Delta x = 0$) bo'lganda esa

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta u &= -b\Delta y - \alpha_2\Delta y \\ \Delta v &= a\Delta y + \alpha_1\Delta y \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

tengliklarga keladi.

(6) munosabatlardan

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = a, \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} = b,$$

(7) munosabatlardan esa

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -b, \quad \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} = a,$$

bo'lishini topamiz. Bu tengliklardan

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial v}{\partial x}$$

bo'lishi kelib chiqadi.

Yetarliligi. Aytaylik $f(z)$ funksiya z_0 nuqtada R^2 ma'noda differensiallanuvchi bo'lib, teoremda keltirilgan ikkinchi shart bajarilsin., $u(x, y)$ va $v(x, y)$ funksiyalar (x_0, y_0) nuqtada differensiallanuvchi bo'lgani uchun

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta u &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \Delta x + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \Delta y + \alpha_1 \Delta x + \alpha_2 \Delta y, \\ \Delta v &= \frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \Delta x + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \Delta y + \beta_1 \Delta x + \beta_2 \Delta y. \end{aligned}$$

bo'ladi. Bu yerda $\Delta x \rightarrow 0$, $\Delta y \rightarrow 0$ da $\alpha_1, \alpha_2, \beta_1, \beta_2$ larning har biri nolga intiladi. U holda

$$\Delta f(z_0) = \Delta u + i\Delta v = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \Delta x + \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} \Delta y + \alpha_1 \Delta x + \alpha_2 \Delta y + i(\frac{\partial v}{\partial x} \Delta x + \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \Delta y + \beta_1 \Delta x + \beta_2 \Delta y)$$

bo'ladi. Teoremaning ikkinchi sharti

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}, \quad \frac{\partial u}{\partial y} = -\frac{\partial v}{\partial x}$$

dan foydalanib topamiz:

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta f(z_0) &= \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} (\Delta x + i\Delta y) - i \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} (\Delta x + i\Delta y) + (\alpha_1 + i\beta_1) \Delta x + (\alpha_2 + i\beta_2) \Delta y = \\ &= \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} \right) \Delta z + \left[(\alpha_1 + i\beta_1) \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta z} + (\alpha_2 + i\beta_2) \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta z} \right] \cdot \Delta z \end{aligned}$$

Bu tenglikda esa

$$\frac{\Delta f(z_0)}{\Delta z} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial v}{\partial y} + (\alpha_1 + i\beta_1) \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta z} + (\alpha_2 + i\beta_2) \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta z}, \quad (8)$$

bo'lishi kelib chiqadi.

Keyingi tenglikdagi

$$(\alpha_1 + i\beta_1) \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta z} + (\alpha_2 + i\beta_2) \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta z}$$

ifoda uchun

$$\left[(\alpha_1 + i\beta_1) \frac{\Delta x}{\Delta z} + (\alpha_2 + i\beta_2) \frac{\Delta y}{\Delta z} \right] \leq [\alpha_1 + i\beta_1] \cdot \left[\frac{\Delta x}{\Delta z} \right] + [\alpha_2 + i\beta_2] \cdot \left[\frac{\Delta y}{\Delta z} \right] \\ \leq [\alpha_1 + i\beta_1] + [\alpha_2 + i\beta_2] \leq |\alpha_1| + |\beta_1| + |\alpha_2| + |\beta_2| < \varepsilon$$

bo'ladi, chunki $\Delta z \rightarrow 0$ da ya'ni $\Delta x \rightarrow 0$ $\Delta y \rightarrow 0$ da

$$\alpha_1 \rightarrow 0, \quad \beta_1 \rightarrow 0, \quad \alpha_2 \rightarrow 0, \quad \beta_2 \rightarrow 0,$$

Shuni e'tiborga olib, $\Delta z \rightarrow 0$ da (8) tenglikda limitga o'tib

$$\lim_{\Delta z \rightarrow 0} \frac{\Delta f(z_0)}{\Delta z} = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}$$

bo'lishini topamiz. Demak, $f(z)$ funksiya z_0 nuqtada $f'(z_0)$ hosilaga ega va

$$f'(z_0) = \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} - i \frac{\partial v}{\partial y}$$

bo'ladi. Teorema isbot bo'ldi.

Teoremada keltirilgan (3) shartlar Koshi-Riman shartlari deyiladi.

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